

Stempladder Technique in Teaching Literature and the Enhancement of Oral Communication among Grade 12 Students

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the significant difference between the scores of the respondents before and after being exposed to stepladder technique in terms of articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions. It sought answers to the questions: What is the pretest score of the respondents before being exposed to stepladder technique in terms of articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions? What is the posttest score of the respondents after being exposed to stepladder technique in terms of articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions? Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after being exposed to stepladder technique in terms of articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions? The respondents underwent the pretest. Then, stepladder technique was applied in the five literary lessons as an intervention. After all the lessons, the posttest was given. Finally, the posttest level of competence is significantly higher than the pretest, thus stepladder technique is effective. There is a significant difference between the respondents' pretest and posttest scores. It improved their oral communication competence such as articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions.

KEYWORDS: Communicative Language Teaching, Oral Communication Competence, Stepladder Technique

INTRODUCTION

On the 15th of May 2013, Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, was accepted to be practiced in the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines. This act gives direction to improve the country's educational system from a 10-year basic education to a 12-year (K to 12) program. Syjueco in 2016 said that this program comprises two-year senior high school level which pertains to a specialized upper-secondary education having core curriculum and diverse tracks. One of the subjects included in this curriculum is the "21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World." The aim is to secure all Filipino high school graduates to have a good understanding regarding the field of literature today.

Broadly, Solmerano, et al. said that people use the word literature to mean written words made to tell stories, dramatize situations, express emotions, analyze and advocate ideas. Composed works before the invention of writing were necessarily spoken or sung and were preserved only as long as living Filipinos knew and performed them.

Nevertheless, the 21st century learners under the K to 12 program found learning English language difficult. Due to pandemic since 2019, many of them experienced speaking difficulties making them hesitant in speaking the language. The JATI-Journal of Southeast Asian Studies released the study of Separa, Generales, and Medina in 2020 regarding the Situational Speaking Difficulties of English as Second Language Learners in the Philippines. The study investigated the contexts wherein second-language speakers of English found difficulty in the various communicative tasks they encountered when dealing with other people. It was asked from university students in the Philippines to recount their experiences using English as a language of oral communication and to describe circumstances which made speaking difficult for them. Data revealed that emerging difficulties in English speaking not only involve lack of linguistic competence but also encompass psycho-social fears of speaking across different communication tasks.

As regards, the stepladder technique exists to aid individuals with speaking difficulties. Sari in 2020 mentioned that in this technique, every member is encouraged to speak and cooperate with the group or team. Through their natural communication, they will feel comfortably included to the circle which will set aside their psycho-social fears in any communication tasks. By their day-by-day communication, they will naturally learn and possess the competence needed for expressing ideas in meaningful situations. Stepladder technique gradually helps the speakers to set aside their worries and give an eye on the given task or problem. Addressing the 21st century learners' difficulties in oral communication, the researcher became enthusiastic in conducting this study on the application of stepladder technique to find a way for an equal chance of learning, sharing ideas and making decisions within a group. This study also aimed to overcome their speaking worries and give a comfortable experience of learning how to speak English language naturally with others.

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OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents before and after being exposed to stepladder technique in terms of articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions. Another goal of this study is to assist the literature instructors who want to make their class communicative and collaborative in terms of learning English language through the application of stepladder technique on their lessons.

Lastly, this study aimed to help the teachers in giving equal chance to each student in terms of sharing ideas and making decisions. Also, this could be a guide on how students undergo the steps of sharing ideas until making final decision in each scenario-based task.

METHODOLOGY

One heterogeneous section, with 40 grade 12 students having an average of 75 to 98, taking 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World under the strand of Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM), handled by the researcher, was selected using purposive sampling for the second quarter of the first semester A.Y. 2022–2023.

The researcher prepared all the instruments such as daily lesson log, analytic rubric, and scenario-based activities for gathering the data. First and foremost, the researcher sent a letter to the San Pablo City – schools division superintendent noted by the principal to ask permission to conduct this study. After the approval, the researcher consulted the thesis adviser regarding the prepared research instruments. The thesis adviser suggested some revisions for the improvement of the paper. After editing it, the researcher sent a letter for validating these instruments to one English subject head and two English teachers. The validators used the validation tool for the instruments. After the process of validation, the researcher sent another letter to the English subject head and the school librarian for asking permission to use these instruments in teaching the subject – 21st Century Literature from the Philippines and the World. After getting the permission, the researcher proceeded to the thesis adviser for the final checking before conducting the study. After getting the signal from the thesis adviser, the researcher began the study.

Conducting this study, the researcher informed the students that they would be the participants or the respondents. The students were grouped into eight with heterogenous members. At this point, the pretest was given. Each group received their own scenario-based activity. They were given five to ten minutes to talk about the problem in the scenario and decide for their final solution. Their conversation happened in a normal forming circle where anyone could speak to share their ideas. Only one group was performing the sharing. After five to ten minutes, the next group followed until all the groups were done. The teacher was actively listening and observing to make careful scoring using the analytic rubric. After the performance of all the groups in the scenario-based activity, the students underwent five lessons with the application of stepladder technique. The students were oriented about the steps to be done using stepladder technique.

In the lesson proper, stepladder technique happened every time after learning a text. The teacher gave a scenario-based activity related to each text. Each member of a group was given a marking number to let them know when they would join the circle. First, in task explanation, one representative from each group explained the task. After that, two to three minutes were given to brainstorm some solutions for the given problem in the texts. Second, in ladder building, two members from each group talked about the scenario and shared their ideas for two minutes. The listener jotted down some errors from the speaker. The third step is the process continuation where after two minutes, the third member would come in and share ideas on how to solve the problem in the given scenario for a minute without the influence of the first two members' shared ideas. The members who shared their ideas already kept themselves silent while the newcomer member was sharing his/her own. The two members just took down the errors that they had observed. The fourth step is the ladder completion. In this step, all must be done sharing. After a minute, the fourth member of each group joined. Then, the fifth member of each group would do the same to complete the group circle. For the fourth and fifth members as speakers during their own minute of sharing, the listeners also jotted down the errors that they observed. The last step is deciding what solution they would take. So, after each member's sharing time, five minutes in total, each group was given an additional five minutes to talk about all their ideas and to decide what ideas they would consider as the best solution for addressing the problem in the scenario. Then, the one who explained the task represented the group to share in front of the class the final decision that they had and how they made it. After the sharing using stepladder technique, each group proceeded to the teacher for the consultation of errors. Processing the errors, the students explained the reasons behind considering it as errors and asked the teacher for suggestions on how they could improve or correct it. After the consultation of all the groups, the teacher shared in front of the class all their common errors and reiterated how to improve it. The class did the same learning routine to the succeeding lessons so they could be exposed to stepladder technique for five times. There was a rotation on whom to explain the task and to share the decision in front of the class. If the student with marking number one from each group represented during the first lesson, the student with marking number two then represented for the next. The third marking number represented the third until the fifth marking number represented the last lesson.

After all the lessons, the students underwent the posttest. Like what they had in the pretest, each group received their own scenario-based activity. Each scenario was different from the pretest to avoid repetition or redundancy and to let them be natural in

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brainstorming and speaking manner with their group mates. This time, they would apply the stepladder technique that they were exposed to during the five lessons. The same analytic rubric was used to evaluate their sharing performance.

After getting the scores from the pretest and posttest, the researcher encoded it and consulted this to the statistician of the study for the statistical tools and treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part presents the findings of the study and their corresponding analysis as well as the interpretation derived from the statistical treatment of the data.

Table 1. Respondents' Oral Communication Competence before being exposed to Stepladder Technique.

	Articulation		Logical Organization		Message		Stage Presence		Facial Expressions	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Advanced	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Proficient	7	17.5%	11	27.5%	15	37.5%	5	12.5%	0	0
Approaching Proficiency	9	22.5%	5	12.5%	1	2.5%	11	27.5%	16	40.0%
Developing	19	47.5%	14	35.0%	18	45.0%	12	30.0%	3	7.5%
Beginning	5	12.5%	10	25.0%	6	15.0%	12	30.0%	21	52.5%

This table shows the results of the respondents' pretest scores. This covers the oral communication competence of the respondents as to articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions before being exposed to stepladder technique.

In articulation, most of the respondents with the percentage of 47.5 were developing this competence. The students somewhat manifested tension. According to Merriam-Webster, tension refers to the inner striving, unrest, or imbalance often with physiological indication of emotion. In a moderate extent, that tension was evident when most of the students stuttered for two to three seconds, used longer fillers like "Ahmm... So... Hmm... Ahh...," and many unnecessary pauses. They also pronounced some words unclearly. Some of them pronounced it unclearly because of the tension they felt while the others were almost laughing during their turn. Laughing while speaking made their vocal cords unprepared to speak due to the air coming out successively and uncontrollably from their diaphragm.

Many of the respondents rated 35% were developing their logical organization as a competence. The students' flow of ideas was fine but they almost lost connections because of some missing transitional words or cohesive devices like using "certainly" or "indeed" to emphasize, and "all in all" or "finally" to summarize what they have talked about or when they had to make decision. In addition, the use of transitional words was too few. Most of them only used one transitional word which made it insufficient in terms of their sentence construction. For example, a member said, "I would like to do the marketing strategy, which are the Irresistible Offer, Sales Panel and Targeting. I'm going to give..." In this construction, it is better to use "For instance," before "I'm going to..." so it will be clearly understood that he was giving example of the strategy that he was suggesting.

Getting a percentage of 45, most of the respondents were also developing their message. They gave ideas that could somehow help to solve the problem in the scenario but there was still a need to improve the clarity of sharing their message. Like the tension mentioned above, it caused most of the respondents to lack clear expressions of their ideas. Most of the ideas were simplistic and lacking the necessary details to better be understood and help to solve the problem in the scenario apparently.

Second to the last is stage presence. The results showed that the majority of the respondents were "Beginning" or "Developing" this competence both getting the percentage of 30. 30% of the students lacked confidence and voice modulation. Many of them could not express their ideas confidently and spoke softly because they seemed to be shy and nervous in speaking. Their shyness and nervousness made them stiff. Their body movements and postures were not effective. Most of their body movements do not face toward their groupmates while their postures looked like old-aged persons who have bones in their spine that creep closer together. Thus, showed discomfort in speaking or simply unwillingness to communicate. Nevertheless, they seemed to be trying to overcome their stage fright which helped them to have a good start in the sharing activity. Meanwhile, the other 30% of the students showed confidence in expressing their ideas but there were times that they lacked modulated voice. Their voices were enough to be heard in the beginning but softened extremely amidst their speaking time. They also showed inadequate connections using their gestures, body movements and postures. They used their hands, moved their bodies, and showed good postures in the beginning but it turned off in the middle of their sharing.

Lastly, most of the respondents with the percentage of 52.5 were in the beginning level of using their facial expressions. The students wore tense or improper facial expressions that interrupted the listeners' attention during the sharing. Their facial muscles were tight or rigid so that only their mouth moved while the others have shown improper facial expressions like laughing which opposed the mood of the given scenario that required serious meeting to brainstorm the most possible solution.

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Table 2. Respondents' Oral Communication Competence after the Exposure to Stepladder Technique.

	Articulation		Logical Organization		Message		Stage Presence		Facial Expressions	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Advanced	18	45.0%	22	55.0%	27	67.5%	10	25.0%	14	35.0%
Proficient	19	47.5%	14	35.0%	11	27.5%	26	65.0%	20	50.0%
Approaching Proficiency	3	7.5%	4	10.0%	2	5.0%	4	10.0%	6	15.0%
Developing	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Beginning	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

This table shows the results of the respondents' posttest scores. This covers the oral communication competence of the respondents as to articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions after being exposed to stepladder technique.

Most of the respondents articulated proficiently after getting a percentage of 47.5 in the first competence. They manifested relaxed and natural pronunciation without using many fillers and stuttering in between. There was no more tension in their pronunciation. They already avoided using many fillers. Also, they pronounced the words clearly and accurately. There was only one unclear word uttered by them. They seriously talked to each other and avoided laughing during their turn, so it made their vocal cords prepared to speak and thus formed correct sounds of the words.

In logical organization, the respondents with the percentage of 55 showed an advanced sharing presentation because they had a very clear delineation of the ideas. They used exact terms or words to explain their ideas in detail. The flow of ideas was logically organized. It was well-connected by transitional words or cohesive devices. The transitional words used were so smooth and very helpful for better understanding. Their use of it did not confuse the listeners about the message they wanted to convey. There were four or more transitional words used that sufficed their message construction. They already seemed to have better knowledge about the use of transitional words. For instance, they used "also" and "and then" for additional ideas, "instead of" and "despite" for contrasting or opposing ideas, and "so" and "all in all" for summarizing ideas.

Moreover, the majority of the respondents with a percentage of 67.5 made and shared an advanced message construction. The students already exceeded the expectations of the teacher through giving clear, unique, and helpful ideas. Their ideas are clear in a way that they provided specific terms and direct explanation. Most of their ideas are unique and contributed to the group's wider solution. Although most members in a group have unique ideas, it contributed to brainstorm for possible solutions. They shared the advantages of taking their ideas into action for a better solution to the problem. Through sharing its advantages, the other members saw the depth and necessity for taking action as a solution to the given problem. They also added other members' ideas.

It emerged in stage presence that most of the respondents were proficient after getting the percentage of 65. The students showed confidence and well-modulated voice. Shyness and nervousness were set aside to show how confident they were in this last speaking activity. Their voices were controlled from soft to loud volume or vice versa depending on the sharing situation that contributed to the understanding of the listeners. Most gestures they used also aid to understand the ideas well. Powerful hand gestures like an open arms and hands with a slight bend at the elbow as a signal that they were confidently sharing their ideas, remaining one palm open and moving gave a strong meaning that the idea has advantages and needed to be taken, two hands steeple or holding both hands let them be active listeners, and a hand in their chest showed sincere ideas or indication to themselves. Body movements and postures were evident and effective. They calmly moved their bodies facing towards the speaker. Also, in speaking, they could control their bodies from left to right or right to left as means for all the members' inclusion in the communication. This time, their postures showed comfort in speaking and willingness to communicate. Their backs were straight, chest out or forward slightly, chin a little upward and downward depending on the needs for sharing their ideas were effective in showing their confidence in speaking. All these things mentioned demonstrated connections with the listeners that contributed to a very good performance.

Lastly, most of the respondents were proficient in using facial expressions to convey ideas after getting the percentage of 50. The students have shown natural, relaxed, and proper facial expressions that comfortably backed the listeners to understand the ideas being shared. Natural facial expressions were shown when they agreed or disagreed with the ideas being shared. For example, they gave a smile with nods when they agreed to a member who was sharing a good or better idea, a smirk or a frown when they disagreed and wanted to contradict other members' ideas, and a serious look like a light squint, neutral face, or tight lips when they actively listened to the speaker. They made those facial expressions in a relaxed and flexible way like at any moment could change depending on their reactions toward the shared ideas. Most importantly, they knew what facial expressions they would use that would fit according to their reactions.

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Table 3. Significant Difference between Pretest and Posttest Scores

	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	M	SD	M	SD			
Articulation	2.45	0.93	4.38	0.63	-12.210	39	0.000
Logical Organization	2.43	1.15	4.45	0.68	-10.596	39	0.000
Message	2.63	1.15	4.63	0.59	-11.909	39	0.000
Stage Presence	2.23	1.03	4.15	0.58	-10.466	39	0.000
Facial Expressions	1.88	0.97	4.20	0.69	-12.187	39	0.000

The p-value is less than the level of significance which is 0.05. The posttest level of competence is significantly higher than the pretest, which means that the stepladder technique is effective. It improved oral communication competence such as articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions.

In articulation, the respondents showed tension in speaking during the pretest. With the five-time stepladder technique experience from the five lessons, the students became comfortable with each other and kept in mind their errors in speaking jotted by their groupmates during the intervention and correct it using the suggestions they asked from their teacher. In the intervention, the teacher included interesting literature for the students to enjoy while reading. They were also required to install Merriam Webster for meaning consultation. According to Maquidato in 2021, utilizing helpful tools such as reading literature or books, and dictionary consultation could help the students who have emotional tensions in speaking English to cope with their nervousness and overcome shyness.

Covering logical organization during the intervention, the students jotted some errors or needed to improve like words connecting their ideas. Consulting to the teacher after the steps in the technique, the students got the term transitional words or cohesive devices. Those were the words that they missed during their communication. In the posttest, they already used transitional words that helped them form their message. According to Smart Words in 2023, transitional words help achieve logical organization. As a part of speech, transitional words are used to link words, phrases, and sentences. It helps the listeners to progress from one idea (expressed by the speaker) to the next and build coherent relationships within the message. It can also improve connections and transitions between sentences and paragraphs.

The intervention focused also on improving the students' natural way of considering clarity of their message through organizing their ideas in abrupt and simplest way yet covering the details of their own thoughts. The students jotted some errors during their groupmates' minute of speaking. They consulted after the steps with the teacher on how they could express their ideas clearly. They were given suggestions like focusing on organizing their thoughts based on the given time, filtering ideas, choosing only the best that would contribute to solving the problem, and being direct in sharing it to others to avoid confusion. According to the Department of Communication in University of Pittsburgh (2015), organizing thoughts helps improve clarity of the message in a systematic way.

The students lacked confidence, voice modulation, proper gestures, and correct posture before their exposure to stepladder technique. During the intervention, they noticed from each other the need to improve their stage presence like what mentioned above so they jotted it and consulted it to the teacher after all the steps. They asked for some suggestions on how to overcome those flaws. They got suggestions like being comfortable with each other, possessing voice control depending on their message, and watching movies and TV shows for adapting meaningful postures and gestures. Also, letting them work in groups and having feedback about their groupmate's performance could improve this competence. According to Seenan et al. in 2016, exposing students to group works or peer feedback increased confidence in skills, especially in communication and teamwork. They added that it is beneficial for students to have an effective learning. According to Van Zant and Berger in 2020, confident speakers who have loud voice and could vary it naturally persuade perceivers' attitudes and choice. Cook added in 2018, gestures are robust behaviors that influence communication and make meaningful learning.

Before the students' exposure to stepladder technique, most of them wore tense or improper facial expressions. Their facial muscles were tight or rigid so only their mouth moved while the others were laughing. During the intervention, many of them noticed that most of those flaws were still existing so they jotted it and consulted the teacher later. They got suggestions like observing others inside and outside their classroom and keeping in mind how those people use facial expressions while talking. As an alternative, they could watch videos or movies to observe the use of facial expressions. After the exposure to stepladder technique, they already have shown natural, relaxed, and proper facial expressions. According to Linkin in 2023, watching others communicate in different situations can help improve one's facial expressions. Mirrors, photos, videos, or applications can be used to observe and to analyze one's own facial expressions. According to Du, Tao and Martinez in 2014, understanding different categories of facial expressions of emotions regularly is essential to gain insights into human cognition and perceptual interfaces, therefore improving communication.

Stepladder technique ensured that everyone in a group would have time to share thoughts equally. This sets aside the traditional sharing in a group that all members could speak at the same time. Like what happened in the pretest, it came out that the other

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members in the traditional sharing became a bit passive and just agreed with the others whom they thought have already given a good idea. Thus, imitated or reconstructed the same ideas that have already been shared. Unlikely, stepladder technique became helpful to the respondents in sharing their unique and probably the best ideas. This also helps an individual to boost confidence in sharing a unique idea that s/he thinks nothing but the most interesting and helpful for a kind of situation like what has been given in each group.

Stepladder technique served as an intervention for the respondents to achieve improvement on their oral communication competence. Students' jotting down errors and their consultation with the teacher helped to improve each competence.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In accordance with the findings of this study, the researcher inferred that the posttest level of competence is significantly higher than the pretest, which means that the stepladder technique is effective. Thus, there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents. It improved oral communication competence such as articulation, logical organization, message, stage presence, and facial expressions.

In line with the findings and conclusion of this study, the researcher recommended the following:

1. For the university or school administrators, they may conduct INSET or seminars regarding stepladder technique to provide good academic programs that highlight the utilization of stepladder technique in teaching English subjects.
2. For the English teachers, since stepladder technique was able to enhance the communicative competence of the students, they are encouraged to use it frequently and share it to other teachers handling other subjects.
3. The students may intensify the part where they identify their errors for enhancement of their oral communication competence.
4. For the readers and future researchers, this study may help them widen their knowledge about stepladder technique and oral communication competence. This may also serve as their guide or reference for their own studies related to this topic.

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